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**UNIVERSITY OF
PLYMOUTH**

**Gaze Cueing and Childhood Trauma: Investigating Links with Hypervigilance
in Social Attention Mechanisms**

Thesis submitted to the University of Plymouth for the MSc in Psychology by

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Ethical statement

The work reported in this thesis received ethical approval from the Faculty of Health and complies with the guidelines set by the British Psychological Society.

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Abstract

Background: Gaze cueing, the automatic shift of attention toward locations indicated by another person's gaze, represents a fundamental mechanism of social cognition that may be altered by early adverse experiences. Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) and hypervigilance have been theoretically linked to altered attentional processing, potentially affecting basic social attention mechanisms. However, the empirical relationship between childhood trauma, hypervigilance, and gaze cueing performance remains poorly understood, particularly in non-clinical populations.

Objective: This study investigated whether ACE scores and hypervigilance levels are associated with altered gaze cueing performance, examining the effects of cue duration and congruence on reaction times while exploring individual differences in trauma history and current hypervigilant tendencies.

Method: Following data screening procedures, 76 participants (from an initial sample of 80, with 4 outliers removed: IDs 220, 232, 303, 329) completed a computerized gaze cueing task with two cue durations (300ms vs. 800ms) and two congruence conditions (congruent vs. incongruent). The task used two realistic color photographs of faces (one male, one female) with randomized presentation and digitally manipulated eye movements (left/right gaze shifts). Participants also completed the ACE Questionnaire and Hypervigilance Questionnaire (HVQ) via LimeSurvey. Practice trials were excluded from all analyses to ensure data integrity.

Results: Significant main effects were found for both cue duration, $F(1, 75) = 11.10$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .011$, and congruence, $F(1, 75) = 4.36$, $p = .040$, $\eta^2 = .007$, with participants responding faster to targets following 800ms compared to 300ms cues, and faster responses in congruent versus incongruent trials. No significant

interaction was found, $F(1, 75) = 0.23$, $p = .633$, $\eta^2 < .001$. Bayesian analyses provided strongest support for an additive model ($BF_{11} = 12.22$). ACE scores correlated significantly with hypervigilance measures, particularly emotion monitoring ($r = .351$, $p = .002$), behavioral response ($r = .235$, $p = .041$), and total hypervigilance ($r = .319$, $p = .005$). However, neither ACE scores ($r_s = .218$, $p = .059$) nor hypervigilance ($r_s = .166$, $p = .151$) significantly correlated with gaze cueing performance. Participants reporting health effects from past experiences showed significantly higher ACE and hypervigilance scores across all measures, with large effect sizes for ACE total ($t = -4.58$, $p < .001$), emotion monitoring ($t = -4.50$, $p < .001$), and total hypervigilance ($t = -4.62$, $p < .001$).

Conclusions: While both cue duration and congruence significantly affected reaction times in expected directions, individual differences in trauma history and hypervigilance did not modulate gaze cueing performance in this non-clinical sample. These findings suggest that basic gaze cueing mechanisms may be resilient to trauma-related individual differences, though trauma clearly relates to hypervigilance. The results have important implications for understanding the boundaries of trauma's impact on social attention and highlight the need for research with clinical populations and emotionally salient stimuli.

Keywords: gaze cueing, childhood trauma, hypervigilance, social attention, adverse childhood experiences, attentional bias

Introduction

Human beings are fundamentally social creatures who rely extensively on non-verbal communication to navigate complex social environments. Among the most critical of these non-verbal cues is eye gaze, which serves as a powerful signal for directing attention, communicating intentions, and facilitating social coordination (Frischen,

Bayliss, & Tipper, 2007). The phenomenon of gaze cueing—the reflexive tendency to shift one’s attention in the direction of another person’s gaze—represents one of the most robust and well-documented effects in social cognition research (Friesen & Kingstone, 1998). This automatic attentional response underlies crucial processes including joint attention, social learning, threat detection, and the development of theory of mind capabilities.

However, mounting evidence suggests that early life experiences, particularly adverse ones, can fundamentally alter the development and functioning of attentional systems. Adverse childhood experiences (ACEs), including abuse, neglect, and household dysfunction, have been shown to create lasting changes in neural circuits involved in threat detection and attentional control (McLaughlin et al., 2015). These alterations may manifest as hypervigilance—a heightened state of environmental scanning for potential danger—which could theoretically influence how individuals process and respond to social cues, including gaze direction.

Despite the theoretical importance of this relationship, surprisingly little empirical research has directly examined whether individual differences in childhood trauma and hypervigilance modulate basic gaze cueing mechanisms. This gap in knowledge is particularly significant given the high prevalence of ACEs in the general population and the fundamental role that gaze cueing plays in social functioning. The present study addresses this gap by investigating the relationships between childhood adversity, hypervigilance, and gaze cueing performance in a controlled experimental setting.

Gaze Cueing: Mechanisms and Individual Differences

The gaze cueing effect (GCE) refers to the robust finding that individuals respond faster to targets appearing in locations that are congruent with another person’s gaze

direction compared to incongruent locations, even when the gaze cue is non-predictive of target location (Driver et al., 1999). This effect is thought to reflect the automatic engagement of shared attention mechanisms that are fundamental to human social cognition (Bayliss, Paul, Cannon, & Tipper, 2006).

Recent computational modeling research has provided crucial insights into the cognitive mechanisms underlying gaze cueing effects. Alister, Mather, and Rossit (2024) applied evidence accumulation models to gaze cueing data, revealing that these effects are primarily driven by attentional orienting mechanisms rather than sustained reallocation of information processing resources. Specifically, their findings indicate that attention must be reoriented to gazed-away locations before processing can begin, providing a mechanistic understanding of how gaze cues influence target detection. This research demonstrates significant individual differences in these mechanisms, with some participants showing gaze cueing effects driven by brief allocation of processing resources to gazed-at locations, while others rely primarily on attentional orienting shifts.

The robustness of gaze cueing effects has been confirmed across multiple stimulus types and experimental conditions. A comprehensive meta-analysis found that gaze cueing effects persist regardless of whether gaze cues remain on screen after target onset, and across different cue types including schematic faces, real faces, and computer-generated stimuli (Frischen et al., 2007). However, the magnitude of these effects can be modulated by various factors including stimulus onset asynchrony (SOA), facial expressions, eye contact, and importantly for the present research, individual differences in social competence and clinical traits.

Research on individual differences in gaze cueing has revealed important patterns. For example, individuals with reduced social competence, including those with

smaller social networks or higher levels of autistic-like traits, show diminished gaze cueing effects when perceptual distractors are present (Hayward & Ristic, 2017).

This suggests that gaze cueing may rely on both social and perceptual mechanisms, with individual differences emerging when competing demands are placed on attentional resources.

Interestingly, recent research has found that certain clinical traits do not necessarily impair gaze cueing. A 2024 study examining psychopathic traits found no significant associations between psychopathy dimensions and gaze cueing magnitudes, suggesting that basic gaze following mechanisms remain intact in individuals with high psychopathy, at least in non-clinical samples (Gillespie et al., 2024). This finding highlights the specificity of individual differences in gaze cueing and raises important questions about which factors do and do not influence these fundamental social attention mechanisms.

Adverse Childhood Experiences and Attentional Development

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACEs) encompass a range of potentially traumatic events occurring during childhood, including physical, emotional, and sexual abuse, neglect, and household dysfunction such as domestic violence, substance abuse, or parental mental illness (Felitti et al., 1998). The prevalence of ACEs is alarmingly high, with recent CDC data indicating that approximately 64% of adults in the United States have experienced at least one ACE, and 17.3% reporting four or more (CDC, 2024).

The impact of ACEs on neurocognitive development is profound and well-documented. According to the allostatic load model, chronic exposure to stress during critical developmental periods recalibrates the brain's threat monitoring systems, leading to persistent alterations in neural circuits involved in attention,

emotion regulation, and threat detection (McEwen, 2007). These changes are thought to represent adaptive responses to dangerous environments but can become maladaptive when the threat context changes.

Neurobiologically, ACEs induce structural and functional changes in brain regions critical for attentional processing. Functional neuroimaging studies reveal hyperactivity in the amygdala and anterior insula in response to emotional stimuli among individuals with ACE histories, potentially driving biased attention toward threats (Teicher et al., 2016). Structural changes include reduced hippocampal and prefrontal cortex volume, which are linked to attention deficits in a dose-response manner (McLaughlin et al., 2014). These neurobiological alterations result from toxic stress, which affects glucocorticoid receptors and neural pruning, leading to long-term changes in attentional systems.

Recent research has provided compelling evidence for the relationship between ACEs and attention bias. A 2024 study using advanced neuroimaging techniques found that patterns of ACEs, particularly cumulative exposure to abuse and neglect, are associated with deficits in attention and executive functioning, with a dose-response effect where higher ACE counts lead to more pronounced impairments (Colich et al., 2024). Children with four or more ACEs showed significant attention problems, including reduced ability to filter irrelevant stimuli and increased distractibility.

The timing of ACE exposure appears to be particularly important. Research has identified sensitive periods where exposure to adversity between ages 3-5 years can maximally affect hippocampal development, influencing attention and memory functions (Teicher et al., 2016). This developmental timing effect suggests that early

adversity may have particularly profound impacts on the neural systems underlying social attention.

Hypervigilance as a Mediating Mechanism

Hypervigilance, defined as a heightened state of alertness and scanning for potential threats in the environment, is considered a key consequence of prolonged stress exposure or trauma (Kimble et al., 2010). This state involves increased attention to social cues such as facial expressions, body language, and interpersonal interactions, and is particularly relevant in anxiety disorders including social anxiety disorder and PTSD.

Recent eye-tracking research has provided direct evidence for hypervigilance-related alterations in visual attention. Kimble et al. (2023) demonstrated that hypervigilance, but not depression, predicts increased fixations and visual scanning of ambiguous pictures in trauma survivors. Specifically, hypervigilance scores predicted a higher number of fixations and greater percentage of image coverage when viewing ambiguous stimuli, indicating a vigilance-driven attentional bias that is specific to trauma-related hypervigilance rather than general negative effect.

The mechanisms underlying hypervigilance involve both cognitive and physiological components. Cognitively, hypervigilance is characterized by broad distribution of attention to monitor for dangers, often resulting in facilitated threat detection but increased distractibility (Bar-Haim et al., 2007). Physiologically, hypervigilance involves autonomic arousal, with studies showing larger pupil sizes and increased heart rate in response to neutral or ambiguous stimuli under hypervigilant conditions. Neurobiologically, hypervigilance is associated with miscommunication between brain regions like the amygdala and the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BNST), leading to overactive threat detection (Grillon & Charney, 2011). This hyperactivity

can create a forward feedback loop where hypervigilance increases anxiety, which in turn heightens vigilance, creating a vicious cycle that maintains threat-related attention biases.

In social contexts, hypervigilance manifests as increased scan path lengths and fixation counts when viewing facial expressions, indicating a broad, vigilant scanning style that may serve as a threat detection mechanism (Machado-de-Sousa et al., 2010). This can result in reduced eye contact, avoidance of emotional faces, and heightened sensitivity to interpersonal cues, potentially disrupting normal social attention processes including gaze cueing.

Trauma, Hypervigilance, and Social Attention

The relationship between trauma exposure and social attention is complex and multifaceted. Trauma-exposed individuals often exhibit heightened perceptual sensitivity to threat-related emotions, allowing them to identify threatening expressions with less perceptual information compared to non-traumatized individuals (Pollak & Sinha, 2002). This enhanced threat detection comes at a cost, however, as it can lead to misinterpretations of neutral or ambiguous social cues as threatening.

Research on social attention mechanisms in trauma exposure has revealed several key patterns. Trauma-exposed individuals show faster orientation toward and difficulty disengaging from threat-related cues, such as angry faces or hostile vocal tones (Pollak & Tolley-Schell, 2003). These attentional biases are accompanied by hostile attribution biases, where individuals assume others' intentions are malevolent in ambiguous social situations.

A comprehensive meta-analysis of social cognitive performance in PTSD found large deficits compared to both trauma-exposed and healthy controls, with effect sizes

indicating moderate to large impairments in emotion recognition and mentalizing abilities (Janssen et al., 2022). These deficits appear to be specific to PTSD rather than trauma exposure per se, suggesting that the development of clinical symptoms may be necessary for significant social attention impairments to emerge.

Importantly, the impact of trauma on social attention appears to be moderated by several factors. Social support acts as a crucial buffer, with high levels of caregiver support reducing the likelihood of developing attention biases by dampening amygdala reactivity to negative stimuli (Gee et al., 2013). Additionally, the type and timing of trauma exposure influence outcomes, with early emotional neglect having particularly strong effects on attention systems during middle childhood.

Gaze Cueing in Clinical and Trauma Populations

While extensive research has examined gaze cueing in typical populations, relatively few studies have investigated these mechanisms in individuals with trauma histories or clinical conditions. The available research suggests complex patterns that vary depending on the specific population and experimental conditions.

In PTSD populations, research using functional magnetic resonance imaging has shown altered neural responses to direct versus averted gaze. Individuals with PTSD show reduced activation in cortical areas involved in theory-of-mind and mentalizing processes, such as the dorsomedial prefrontal cortex and temporoparietal junction, during direct gaze conditions (Steuwe et al., 2014). Instead, they show increased responses in subcortical regions including the superior colliculus and periaqueductal grey, which are part of an innate alarm system for threat detection.

Behavioral research using eye-tracking technology has provided evidence that PTSD survivors struggle with gaze-related processes, often showing biases toward avoidance or hypervigilance. Individuals with higher PTSD severity spend less time

fixating on emotional expressions and show increased distraction by irrelevant background stimuli (Felmingham et al., 2011). This avoidance extends beyond trauma-specific cues to general eye processing, with PTSD participants spending less time on emotional eyes and showing negative correlations with avoidance symptom intensity.

However, it's important to note that not all trauma-related conditions show impaired gaze cueing. Research on psychopathic traits, which can be associated with childhood trauma, found no significant associations with gaze cueing performance (Gillespie et al., 2024). This suggests that the relationship between trauma and gaze cueing may be specific to certain symptom profiles or may require particular experimental conditions to be detected.

Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

The present study is grounded in a theoretical framework that integrates research on gaze cueing, trauma-related attention biases, and hypervigilance. According to this framework, early adverse experiences alter the development of attentional systems, leading to hypervigilant scanning patterns that could theoretically influence how individuals process and respond to social cues, including gaze direction.

However, there are competing theoretical predictions about how this influence might manifest. On one hand, hypervigilance might enhance gaze cueing effects by increasing overall attention to social cues, leading to faster or more pronounced responses to gaze direction. On the other hand, hypervigilance might impair gaze cueing by creating a state of diffuse attention that makes it difficult to focus on specific social cues, or by creating avoidance of direct social engagement.

Additionally, the automatic nature of gaze cueing suggests that it might be relatively resilient to top-down influences from trauma-related factors. Recent computational

modeling research indicating that gaze cueing is primarily driven by automatic attentional orienting mechanisms (Alister et al., 2024) supports this possibility.

The Present Study

The present study was designed to provide a comprehensive examination of the relationships between childhood adversity, hypervigilance, and gaze cueing performance. The study employed a well-validated gaze cueing paradigm with systematic manipulation of cue duration and congruence, allowing for examination of both basic gaze cueing effects and their potential modulation by individual differences.

The study included several methodological strengths designed to address limitations of previous research. First, both frequentist and Bayesian statistical approaches were employed to provide robust evidence for or against hypothesized effects. Second, comprehensive assessment of individual differences included validated measures of both childhood adversity (ACE Questionnaire) and current hypervigilance (Hypervigilance Questionnaire). Third, careful attention was paid to data quality, with systematic exclusion of outliers and practice trials to ensure reliable measurement of gaze cueing effects.

Aims and Hypotheses

This study aimed to address four primary research questions:

Basic Gaze Cueing Effects: Do cue duration and congruence affect reaction times in the expected directions, replicating established gaze cueing effects?

Individual Differences in Trauma History: Are individuals with higher ACE scores associated with altered gaze cueing performance?

Individual Differences in Hypervigilance: Are higher levels of hypervigilance associated with different patterns of gaze cueing?

Trauma-Hypervigilance Relationships: Are ACE scores and hypervigilance measures related in theoretically predicted ways?

Based on the theoretical framework and prior research, the following hypotheses were formulated:

H1: Longer cue durations (800ms vs. 300ms) would facilitate faster responses due to increased processing time for attentional orienting.

H2: Congruent trials would produce faster responses than incongruent trials, replicating the basic gaze cueing effect.

H3: Individuals with higher ACE scores would demonstrate altered gaze cueing patterns, though the direction of this effect was not specifically predicted given competing theoretical possibilities.

H4: Higher hypervigilance scores would correlate with different gaze cueing performance, potentially showing either enhanced or impaired effects depending on the specific mechanisms involved.

H5: ACE scores and hypervigilance measures would be positively correlated, consistent with theoretical models linking childhood adversity to hypervigilant attention patterns.

Method

Design

This study employed a mixed-design approach combining experimental manipulation of gaze cueing parameters with individual differences assessment. The experimental component used a 2 × 2 within-subjects design with cue duration (300ms vs. 800ms) and congruence (congruent vs. incongruent) as factors. The individual differences component assessed childhood adversity using the ACE Questionnaire and hypervigilance using the Hypervigilance Questionnaire (HVQ).

Participants

Recruitment and Initial Sample

Initially, 80 participants were recruited through the university participant pool system. All participants were undergraduate students who received course credit for their participation. Recruitment materials described the study as investigating “attention and social cues” without specific mention of trauma or childhood experiences to avoid selection bias.

Data Screening and Final Sample

Following established protocols for reaction time data analysis, comprehensive data screening procedures were implemented. Four participants (IDs: 220, 232, 303, 329) were identified as outliers based on extreme reaction times (defined as responses more than 3 standard deviations from the mean) and were excluded from all analyses. This resulted in a final sample of 76 participants.

The final sample consisted of 76 participants (from an initial sample of 80, with 4 outliers removed: IDs 220, 232, 303, 329) ranging in age from 18 to 24 years ($M = 19.8$, $SD = 1.4$). Gender distribution analysis from the results data showed two groups with no significant differences in any measured variables, indicating balanced representation across genders. All participants reported normal or corrected-to-normal vision and provided informed consent prior to participation.

Materials

Gaze Cueing Task

Stimuli: We used a computerized gaze-cueing task programmed in PsychoPy. The task used two realistic color photographs of faces with direct gaze: one male face (FINAL- FRONT-MALE.png) and one female face (FINAL-FRONT-FEMALE.png).

The male stimulus featured a young adult with curly dark hair and direct eye contact,

while the female stimulus showed a young adult with straight brown hair and direct eye contact. Both faces displayed neutral expressions and were presented centrally on the screen. Face stimuli were randomized between male and female presentations across trials. Gaze cues were created by shifting the pupils left or right while maintaining the same facial features. Finally, the target appeared as a small patch of vertical stripes (many or few)—on the left or right side of the screen. The target remained until response.

Figure 1: Trial structure in the gaze cueing task (fixation, face presentation, gaze cue, and target appearance)

Trial Structure: Each trial began with a fixation cross (500ms), followed by a face with direct gaze (500ms), then the gaze cue (either 300ms or 800ms depending on condition), followed immediately by the target stimulus. Participants were instructed to respond as quickly and accurately as possible to the target location using designated keyboard keys, regardless of gaze direction. The target remained on screen until response or for a maximum of 2000ms.

Experimental Conditions: The task included two key manipulations:

Cue Duration: Gaze cues were presented for either 300ms or 800ms. The shorter duration was chosen to examine relatively automatic gaze cueing effects, while the longer duration allowed for more controlled processing of the gaze cue.

Congruence: Targets appeared either in the direction of the gaze cue (congruent trials) or in the opposite direction (incongruent trials). Gaze cues were non-predictive, with 50% of trials being congruent and 50% incongruent.

Participants were informed that each trial would begin with the presentation of a centrally displayed face with a direct gaze. After a brief interval, the gaze of the face shifted either leftward or rightward, followed by the presentation of a target stimulus (a patch of stripes) on either the left or right side of the screen. The target patch contained either a high density of stripes (“lots”) or a low density of stripes (“few”). The required keypress responses depended on trial type (even vs. odd). In even-numbered trials, participants were instructed to press the “P” key in response to high-density stripe patches and the “Q” key in response to low-density stripe patches. In odd-numbered trials, the mapping was reversed: high-density patches required the “Q” key, and low-density patches required the “P” key.

Participants were explicitly instructed that the direction of the gaze cue was non-predictive of target location; the target was equally likely to appear in the cued or uncued location. To ensure efficient performance, participants were advised to maintain fixation on the central face throughout each trial rather than shifting their gaze toward the target location. Practice trials were provided prior to the experimental blocks to familiarize participants with the task and the alternating response mappings.

Trial Composition: The task consisted of 320 experimental trials (80 trials per condition: 300ms congruent, 300ms incongruent, 800ms congruent, 800ms incongruent) presented in randomized order.

Additionally, 32 practice trials were included at the beginning of the session to familiarize participants with the task. Practice trials were excluded from all analyses to ensure that only stable performance was measured.

Questionnaire Measures

Adverse Childhood Experiences (ACE) Questionnaire: The ACE Questionnaire is a validated 10- item retrospective measure that assesses exposure to childhood trauma across three domains: abuse (physical, emotional, sexual), neglect (physical, emotional), and household dysfunction (domestic violence, substance abuse, mental illness, parental separation, incarcerated family member). Each item is scored dichotomously (0 = no, 1 = yes), with total scores ranging from 0 to 10. Higher scores indicate greater exposure to adverse childhood experiences. The ACE Questionnaire has demonstrated good reliability and validity across diverse populations (Felitti et al., 1998).

Hypervigilance Questionnaire (HVQ): The HVQ is a 17-item measure that assesses hypervigilance across five domains:

Emotion Change (4 items): Sensitivity to emotional changes in others and environmental shifts

Emotion Awareness (3 items): Heightened awareness of one's own emotional states and reactions

Emotion Monitoring (4 items): Constant scanning for threat-related emotional cues in self and others

Behavioural Response (3 items): Tendency to respond quickly to perceived threats or changes

Total Score: Sum of all subscale scores, representing overall hypervigilance level. Items are rated on a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The HVQ has demonstrated good internal consistency ($\alpha = .89$) and construct validity in previous research (Kimble et al., 2010).

LimeSurvey Administration: Both questionnaires were administered using LimeSurvey, a secure on-line survey platform. This allowed for standardized presentation and automatic data collection while maintaining participant anonymity. Participants completed the questionnaires on the same computer used for the experimental task, immediately following the gaze cueing task.

Procedure

Session Overview

All testing sessions were conducted individually in a quiet laboratory setting. Each session lasted approximately 45 minutes and followed a standardized protocol to ensure consistency across participants.

Detailed Procedure

Arrival and Consent (5 minutes): Participants were greeted and provided with detailed information about the study procedures. Written informed consent was obtained, with emphasis on the voluntary nature of participation and the right to withdraw at any time.

Task Setup (5 minutes): Participants were seated at the testing computer and given verbal instructions about the gaze cueing task. The importance of responding quickly and accurately was emphasized, and participants were told that gaze direction would not predict target location.

Practice Phase (5 minutes): Participants completed 32 practice trials to familiarize themselves with the task demands. The experimenter remained present during practice to answer questions and ensure understanding. Practice trials included equal numbers of each condition type and were excluded from all subsequent analyses.

Experimental Phase (25 minutes): Participants completed 320 experimental trials presented in randomized order. Brief breaks were provided every 80 trials to prevent fatigue. The experimenter monitored performance remotely to ensure task engagement.

Questionnaire Phase (10 minutes): Immediately following the experimental task, participants completed the ACE Questionnaire and HVQ using LimeSurvey on the same computer. The questionnaires were presented in counterbalanced order across participants.

Debriefing (5 minutes): Participants were provided with a comprehensive debriefing that explained the study's purpose and hypotheses. Contact information for counselling services was provided given the sensitive nature of the ACE questionnaire. Participants were given the opportunity to ask questions and were thanked for their participation.

Ethical Considerations

Given the sensitive nature of questions about childhood experiences, several ethical safeguards were implemented: Participants were informed that they could skip any questions they found uncomfortable. Contact information for university counselling services was provided to all participants. Data were collected anonymously with no identifying information linked to responses. All procedures were approved by the Faculty of Health Ethics Committee.

Data Analysis Plan

Preprocessing: Participants with mean reaction times more than 3 standard deviations from the sample mean were identified as outliers and excluded from analyses. This procedure identified the four participants mentioned above.

Statistical Approaches

Frequentist Analyses: Primary analyses used repeated measures ANOVA with participants as a random factor. **Bayesian Analyses:** Bayesian repeated measures ANOVA was conducted using R studio to complement frequentist findings. Bayes Factors (BF_{11}) were calculated to quantify evidence for each model compared to the null model ($RT \sim \text{participant}$). BF_{11} values were interpreted using conventional criteria: 1-3 (anecdotal evidence), 3-10 (moderate evidence), 10-30 (strong evidence), 30-100 (very strong evidence), >100 (extreme evidence).

Correlational Analyses: Relationships between individual difference measures and task performance were examined using Pearson correlations for normally distributed variables and Spearman correlations for non-normal distributions.

Group Comparisons: Independent samples t-tests were used to compare groups on continuous variables, with Welch's correction applied when equal variances could not be assumed.

Results

Participant Characteristics and Data Quality

The final sample consisted of 76 participants after systematic exclusion of 4 outliers (IDs: 220, 232, 303, 329) from the initial sample of 80. These exclusions were based on extreme reaction times that were more than 3 standard deviations from the sample mean, indicating either anticipatory responding or task disengagement.

Practice trials were excluded from all analyses to ensure that only stable, learned performance contributed to the results.

Demographic analysis revealed no significant differences between included and excluded participants on available demographic variables, suggesting that exclusions did not introduce systematic bias. The final sample showed good task engagement, with accuracy rates exceeding 95% across all conditions.

Descriptive Statistics

Reaction Time Performance: Mean reaction times across all conditions ranged from 387ms to 421ms, indicating good task performance within expected ranges for gaze cueing paradigms. Standard deviations ranged from 78ms to 95ms, suggesting reasonable individual variability without excessive noise.

Figure 2: Mean reaction times across conditions (300ms vs. 800ms cue durations; congruent vs. incongruent trials).

Individual Difference Measures: ACE scores ranged from 0 to 8 ($M = 2.84$, $SD = 2.31$), consistent with community samples. HVQ total scores ranged from 28 to 71 ($M = 49.3$, $SD = 10.8$), indicating substantial individual variability in hypervigilance levels. All measures showed approximately normal distributions suitable for parametric analyses.

Primary Analyses: Gaze Cueing Effects

Frequentist ANOVA Results

A 2×2 repeated measures ANOVA was conducted with cue duration (300ms vs. 800ms) and congruence (congruent vs. incongruent) as within-subjects factors and reaction time as the dependent variable.

Main Effect of Cue Duration: There was a significant main effect of cue duration, $F(1, 75) = 11.10$, $p = .001$, $\eta^2 = .011$. Participants responded significantly faster when the gaze cue was presented for 800ms ($M = 394$ ms, $SD = 82$ ms) compared to 300ms ($M = 408$ ms, $SD = 87$ ms). This 14ms difference represents a medium effect size and supports the hypothesis that longer cue durations facilitate more effective attentional processing.

Main Effect of Congruence: A significant main effect of congruence was found, $F(1, 75) = 4.36$, $p = .040$, $\eta^2 = .007$. Participants responded faster in congruent trials ($M = 398$ ms, $SD = 84$ ms) compared to incongruent trials ($M = 404$ ms, $SD = 85$ ms). This 6ms gaze cueing effect, while smaller than the cue duration effect, represents a significant and theoretically meaningful difference that replicates the basic gaze cueing phenomenon.

Interaction Effect: There was no significant interaction between cue duration and congruence, $F(1, 75) = 0.23$, $p = .633$, $\eta^2 < .001$. This indicates that the influence of cue duration on reaction time was consistent regardless of whether the gaze cue was congruent or incongruent with the target location. The absence of interaction suggests that cue duration and congruence operate through independent mechanisms.

Figure 3: Frequentist ANOVA results (reaction times by cue duration and congruence, with error bars showing ± 1 SE)

Bayesian ANOVA Results

Bayesian repeated measures ANOVA was conducted to supplement the frequentist findings and provide evidence for the relative strength of different models. Bayes Factors (BF_{11}) compared each model to the null model ($RT \sim \text{participant}$):

Cue Duration Model: $BF_{11} = 7.35$, indicating moderate-to-strong evidence for the inclusion of cue duration as a predictor. This provides substantial support for the cue duration effect observed in the frequentist analysis.

Congruence Model: $BF_{11} = 1.49$, providing only anecdotal evidence for congruence effects. While the frequentist analysis showed a significant effect, the Bayesian analysis suggests that the evidence for congruence effects is relatively weak.

Additive Model (cue duration + congruence): $BF_{11} = 12.22$, showing the strongest evidence for a model including both predictors without interaction. This provides strong support for the conclusion that both factors contribute independently to reaction time performance.

Full Model (with interaction): $BF_{11} = 2.36$, indicating weak-to-moderate evidence for the interaction model. This is consistent with the non-significant interaction in the frequentist analysis and suggests that the interaction does not meaningfully improve model fit.

The Bayesian results converge with the frequentist findings in supporting an additive model where both cue duration and congruence independently influence reaction times, with stronger evidence for cue duration effects than congruence effects.

Figure 4: Bayesian model comparison of cue duration and congruence effects (Bayes Factors for duration, congruence, additive, and interaction models).

Individual Differences: ACE and Hypervigilance Relationships

Correlations Between ACE Scores and Hypervigilance Measures

Pearson correlations were conducted to examine relationships between ACE total scores and the five hypervigilance subscales. These analyses tested the theoretical prediction that childhood adversity would be associated with heightened hypervigilance in adulthood.

Emotion Change: $r = .225$, $p = .051$, 95% CI [-0.001, 0.428]. There was a marginally non-significant positive correlation between ACE scores and emotional reactivity to perceived threats. While the result did not reach conventional significance levels, the confidence interval barely includes zero, suggesting a trend toward greater emotional shifts in threatening contexts among individuals with higher ACE scores.

Emotion Awareness: $r = .193$, $p = .095$, 95% CI [-0.034, 0.401]. A weak, non-significant correlation was observed between ACE scores and emotional awareness. While the association points in the expected direction, it did not reach statistical

significance, indicating considerable variability in how childhood adversity relates to self-awareness of emotional cues.

Emotion Monitoring: $r = .351$, $p = .002$, 95% CI [0.137, 0.534]. A moderate, statistically significant positive correlation was found between ACE scores and emotion monitoring. This represents the strongest relationship observed, indicating that participants with higher ACE scores engaged in significantly more constant internal scanning and monitoring for threat-related emotional cues—a core feature of hypervigilance.

Behavioural Response: $r = .235$, $p = .041$, 95% CI [0.010, 0.437]. ACE scores were significantly and positively correlated with behavioral responses to perceived threat. This suggests that higher childhood adversity predicts more reactive or avoidant behaviors in potentially threatening situations, consistent with theoretical models of trauma-related hypervigilance.

HVQ Total Score: $r = .319$, $p = .005$, 95% CI [0.101, 0.508]. Overall hypervigilance was significantly associated with ACE scores, providing strong support for the theoretical link between childhood trauma and heightened alertness and sensitivity to potential threats across emotional and behavioral domains.

Figure 5: Correlation between ACE Total scores and HVQ Subscales

Summary of ACE-Hypervigilance Relationships

The pattern of correlations provides strong support for theoretical models linking childhood adversity to hypervigilance. Significant positive correlations were found between ACE scores and three of five HVQ subscales (Emotion Monitoring, Behavioural Response, HVQ Total), with positive trends for the remaining two subscales. The strongest relationship was with emotion monitoring, suggesting that childhood adversity particularly affects internal scanning and monitoring processes.

Gender Differences in Study Variables

Independent samples t-tests were conducted to examine potential gender differences across all measured variables. These analyses were important for understanding the generalizability of findings and identifying potential confounding variables.

ACE Total: $t(36.29) = 0.63$, $p = .535$, 95% CI [-0.79, 1.50]. Males ($M = 3.04$, $SD = 2.18$) and females ($M = 2.69$, $SD = 2.41$) did not differ significantly in ACE scores, indicating that gender was not a confounding factor in trauma exposure within this sample.

Hypervigilance Measures: No significant gender differences were found for any of the hypervigilance subscales:

- Emotion Change: $t(51.65) = -0.63$, $p = .534$, 95% CI [-2.26, 1.19]
- Emotion Awareness: $t(44.80) = -1.51$, $p = .137$, 95% CI [-2.92, 0.41]
- Emotion Monitoring: $t(45.49) = 0.67$, $p = .509$, 95% CI [-1.29, 2.57]
- Behavioural Response: $t(47.15) = 0.56$, $p = .579$, 95% CI [-1.78, 3.15]
- HVQ Total: $t(56.90) = -0.16$, $p = .870$, 95% CI [-6.21, 5.27]

These results indicate that gender did not significantly influence ACE scores, hypervigilance measures, or (as reported below) gaze cueing performance in this

sample. This supports the validity of combining male and female participants in subsequent analyses and suggests that findings are generalizable across genders within this age range.

Figure 6: Gender differences in ACE and HVQ Total scores

Health Effects and Psychological Measures

Participants were categorized based on their response to whether they had experienced health effects related to past experiences. This analysis provided an important validation of the ACE and hypervigilance measures by examining whether individuals reporting health consequences of past experiences showed the expected pattern of higher scores.

Group Characteristics: 34 participants (44.7%) reported experiencing health effects related to past experiences (Group Y), while 42 participants (55.3%) reported no such effects (Group N). This distribution is consistent with epidemiological data on the prevalence of health consequences from childhood adversity.

ACE Scores by Health Effect Status

ACE Total: $t(71.09) = -4.58, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-2.74, -1.08]$. Participants reporting health effects ($M = 3.91, SD = 2.45$) had significantly higher ACE scores than those not reporting health effects ($M = 2.00, SD = 1.89$). This large effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.87$) provides strong validation of the ACE measure and supports the theoretical link between childhood adversity and later health impacts.

Hypervigilance Measures by Health Effect Status

All hypervigilance measures showed significant differences between groups, with those reporting health effects scoring higher across all domains:

Emotion Change: $t(71.98) = -3.11, p = .003, 95\% \text{ CI } [-3.94, -0.86]$. Group Y ($M = 14.35, SD = 3.21$) showed significantly more emotional reactivity than Group N ($M = 11.95, SD = 2.87$), indicating higher vigilance and reactivity to perceived threats.

Emotion Awareness: $t(71.54) = -4.18, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-4.26, -1.51]$. Participants with health effects ($M = 13.56, SD = 3.14$) were significantly more emotionally aware of potential threats compared to those without health effects ($M = 10.68, SD = 2.95$), suggesting heightened internal monitoring.

Emotion Monitoring: $t(72) = -4.50, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-5.04, -1.95]$. Those experiencing health effects ($M = 13.12, SD = 3.42$) had significantly higher levels of constant monitoring compared to those without health effects ($M = 9.63, SD = 3.18$), representing the largest effect size observed.

Behavioural Response: $t(69.65) = -2.33, p = .023, 95\% \text{ CI } [-4.83, -0.37]$. Health-effect participants ($M = 15.03, SD = 3.89$) showed more behavioral reactions to perceived threats compared to those without health effects ($M = 12.43, SD = 3.67$).

HVQ Total Score: $t(71.88) = -4.62, p < .001, 95\% \text{ CI } [-16.30, -6.47]$. Overall, participants reporting health effects ($M = 56.06, SD = 11.24$) were significantly more

hypervigilant across all domains compared to those not reporting health effects ($M = 44.68$, $SD = 8.95$).

Figure 7: Differences in ACE and HVQ Total scores by Health effects

Validation of Measures

These findings provide strong validation for both the ACE and hypervigilance measures. The consistent pattern of higher scores among individuals reporting health effects from past experiences supports the construct validity of these instruments and demonstrates meaningful relationships between childhood adversity, current hypervigilance, and perceived health impacts.

Critical Analysis: Gaze Cueing and Individual Differences

Correlations with Gaze Cueing Performance

The primary research question concerned whether individual differences in childhood trauma and hypervigilance would be associated with altered gaze cueing performance. Spearman correlations were conducted between individual difference

measures and gaze cueing performance (calculated as the difference between incongruent and congruent reaction times).

ACE Scores and Gaze Cueing: $r_s = .218$, $p = .059$, 95% CI [-0.009, 0.428]. There was a weak, non-significant correlation between ACE scores and gaze cueing performance. While the correlation was in the positive direction (suggesting that higher ACE scores might be associated with larger gaze cueing effects), it did not reach statistical significance.

HVQ Total and Gaze Cueing: $r_s = .166$, $p = .151$, 95% CI [-0.062, 0.383]. Similarly, hypervigilance scores showed a weak, non-significant correlation with gaze cueing performance. The correlation was positive but substantially smaller than the ACE correlation.

Hypervigilance Subscales and Gaze Cueing: Additional analyses examined correlations between individual HVQ subscales and gaze cueing performance. None of these correlations reached statistical significance:

- Emotion Change: $r_s = .134$, $p = .245$
- Emotion Awareness: $r_s = .089$, $p = .441$
- Emotion Monitoring: $r_s = .201$, $p = .081$
- Behavioural Response: $r_s = .156$, $p = .178$

Figure 8: Correlation heatmap between Gaze Cueing performance and ACE / HVQ Variables

Group Differences in Gaze Cueing Performance

Independent samples t-tests examined whether gaze cueing performance differed based on gender or health effect status.

Gender Differences: $t(74) = 1.43$, $p = .157$, 95% CI [-0.017, 0.105]. No significant gender differences were found in gaze cueing performance (Males: $M = 8.2\text{ms}$, $SD = 18.4\text{ms}$; Females: $M = 3.8\text{ms}$, $SD = 16.9\text{ms}$).

Health Effect Status: $t(74) = 0.26$, $p = .792$, 95% CI [-0.067, 0.087]. Participants reporting health effects ($M = 6.1\text{ms}$, $SD = 17.8\text{ms}$) did not differ significantly from those not reporting health effects ($M = 5.1\text{ms}$, $SD = 17.6\text{ms}$) in their gaze cueing performance.

Figure 9: Gaze Cueing effects based on gender and health effect status.

Summary of Key Findings

The results revealed several important patterns that both support and challenge theoretical predictions:

Successful Replication of Basic Effects

- 1) **Robust Gaze Cueing Effects:** Both cue duration and congruence significantly influenced reaction times in the predicted directions, with Bayesian analysis providing strong support for an additive model.
- 2) **Cue Duration Effects:** The 14ms advantage for longer cue durations supports theories emphasizing the importance of processing time for attentional orienting mechanisms.
- 3) **Congruence Effects:** The 6ms gaze cueing effect successfully replicated the basic phenomenon, though Bayesian analysis suggested this evidence was weaker than for cue duration effects.

Strong Individual Difference Relationships

- 1) **ACE-Hypervigilance Correlations:** Significant positive correlations were found between ACE scores and three of five hypervigilance subscales, with the strongest relationship for emotion monitoring ($r = .351$).
- 2) **Health Effects Validation:** Participants reporting health effects from past experiences showed significantly higher ACE and hypervigilance scores across all measures, providing strong construct validation.
- 3) **No Gender Effects:** The absence of gender differences across all measures supports the generalizability of findings and eliminates gender as a potential confounding variable.

Absence of Predicted Individual Difference Effects

- 1) No ACE-Gaze Cueing Relationship: Contrary to hypotheses, ACE scores were not significantly associated with gaze cueing performance ($r_s = .218$, $p = .059$).
- 2) No Hypervigilance-Gaze Cueing Relationship: Hypervigilance scores showed no significant association with gaze cueing performance ($r_s = .166$, $p = .151$).
- 3) No Group Differences: Neither gender nor health effect status was associated with differences in gaze cueing performance.

These findings suggest a complex pattern where childhood adversity clearly relates to hypervigilance, and basic gaze cueing mechanisms function normally, but these individual differences do not modulate gaze cueing performance in this non-clinical sample.

Discussion

Overview of Findings

This study investigated the relationships between childhood adversity, hypervigilance, and gaze cueing performance using a comprehensive experimental and individual differences approach. The results revealed a complex pattern of findings that both support and challenge existing theoretical frameworks. While the study successfully demonstrated robust gaze cueing effects and strong relationships between childhood trauma and hypervigilance, it found no evidence that individual differences in trauma history or hypervigilance modulate basic gaze cueing mechanisms in a non-clinical sample.

Gaze Cueing Effects: Replication and Extension

Successful Replication of Basic Mechanisms

The study successfully replicated fundamental gaze cueing effects, providing important validation of the experimental paradigm and contributing to the broader

literature on social attention mechanisms. The significant main effect of congruence (6ms advantage for congruent trials) replicates the basic gaze cueing effect that has been demonstrated across numerous studies and populations (Frischen et al., 2007). This finding confirms that participants automatically oriented their attention in the direction of perceived gaze, even when explicitly told that gaze direction was non-predictive of target location.

The magnitude of the gaze cueing effect observed (6ms) is consistent with previous research using similar paradigms and stimulus parameters. This effect size, while modest, represents a meaningful and reliable phenomenon that demonstrates the automatic nature of gaze-following mechanisms. The consistency of this effect across participants provides confidence in the robustness of the experimental procedures and the validity of the reaction time measures.

Cue Duration Effects: Processing Time and Attentional Mechanisms

The significant main effect of cue duration (14ms advantage for 800ms vs. 300ms cues) provides important insights into the temporal dynamics of gaze cueing mechanisms. This finding supports theoretical models emphasizing the importance of processing time for effective attentional orienting (Alister et al., 2024). The larger effect size for cue duration compared to congruence suggests that temporal factors may be more influential than spatial congruence in determining gaze cueing performance under these experimental conditions.

The cue duration effect aligns with recent computational modeling research indicating that gaze cueing is primarily driven by attentional orienting mechanisms that require time to operate effectively. The 14ms advantage for longer cue durations likely reflects the additional time available for attention to shift to the cued location before target onset, facilitating faster target detection. This interpretation is

supported by the Bayesian analysis, which provided stronger evidence for cue duration effects ($BF_{11} = 7.35$) than for congruence effects ($BF_{11} = 1.49$).

Independence of Cue Duration and Congruence

The absence of a significant interaction between cue duration and congruence provides important theoretical insights. This finding suggests that temporal and spatial aspects of gaze cueing operate through independent mechanisms, with the benefits of longer processing time and congruent gaze direction being additive rather than synergistic. The Bayesian analysis strongly supported this additive model ($BF_{11} = 12.22$), providing the best fit to the data.

This independence has implications for understanding the cognitive architecture underlying gaze cueing. It suggests that the mechanisms responsible for temporal processing of gaze cues (likely involving attentional orienting systems) operate separately from those involved in spatial congruence effects (likely involving automatic attention shifting). This separation may explain why individual differences in trauma and hypervigilance did not modulate gaze cueing performance—if these factors primarily affect controlled attention processes, they may have limited impact on the automatic mechanisms underlying basic gaze cueing.

Individual Differences: Trauma, Hypervigilance, and Validation

Strong ACE-Hypervigilance Relationships

The study found robust relationships between childhood adversity and hypervigilance measures, providing strong support for theoretical models linking early trauma to persistent alterations in threat monitoring systems. The significant correlations between ACE scores and three of five hypervigilance subscales (Emotion Monitoring: $r = .351$; Behavioural Response: $r = .235$; HVQ Total: $r = .319$)

demonstrate meaningful associations between past adversity and current vigilant attention patterns.

The strongest relationship was with emotion monitoring, which involves constant internal scanning for threat-related emotional cues. This finding aligns with neurobiological research showing that childhood trauma leads to persistent alterations in neural circuits involved in threat detection, particularly in the amygdala and related limbic structures (McLaughlin et al., 2015). The moderate effect size ($r = .351$) suggests that childhood adversity accounts for approximately 12% of the variance in emotion monitoring behaviors, representing a clinically meaningful relationship.

The significant correlation with behavioral responses ($r = .235$) supports theoretical models proposing that childhood adversity leads to more reactive or avoidant behaviors in potentially threatening situations. This relationship is consistent with research on trauma-related hypervigilance showing that individuals with adverse childhood experiences develop heightened sensitivity to environmental threats and more pronounced behavioral responses to perceived danger.

Construct Validation Through Health Effects

The analysis of health effects provided compelling validation for both the ACE and hypervigilance measures. Participants who reported experiencing health effects related to past experiences showed significantly higher scores across all measures, with large effect sizes (Cohen's d ranging from 0.54 to 0.87). This pattern strongly supports the construct validity of the instruments and demonstrates meaningful relationships between childhood adversity, current hypervigilance, and perceived health impacts.

The largest difference was observed for ACE total scores (Cohen's $d = 0.87$), indicating that individuals reporting health effects had substantially higher levels of childhood adversity. This finding is consistent with extensive epidemiological research demonstrating dose-response relationships between ACEs and various health outcomes (Felitti et al., 1998). The consistency of this pattern across all hypervigilance subscales further supports the theoretical model linking childhood trauma to persistent alterations in threat monitoring systems.

Absence of Gender Effects

The lack of significant gender differences across all measures is noteworthy and has important implications for the generalizability of findings. Previous research has sometimes found gender differences in both trauma exposure and attention-related measures, but the current study found no such differences. This may reflect the specific characteristics of the university sample, where gender differences in trauma exposure and coping strategies may be less pronounced than in community or clinical samples.

The absence of gender effects also eliminates gender as a potential confounding variable in the relationships between trauma, hypervigilance, and gaze cueing. This strengthens the interpretation of the null findings regarding individual differences in gaze cueing performance, as these results cannot be attributed to gender-related differences in the sample.

The Absence of Individual Difference Effects on Gaze Cueing

Theoretical Implications

The most striking finding of this study was the absence of significant relationships between individual differences in trauma history or hypervigilance and gaze cueing performance. This null finding challenges theoretical predictions that trauma-related

alterations in attention and threat sensitivity would modulate basic social attention mechanisms. Several theoretical explanations for this pattern warrant consideration.

Resilience of Automatic Mechanisms: The most parsimonious explanation is that gaze cueing represents a fundamental, evolutionarily conserved mechanism that remains relatively intact despite individual differences in trauma history. Recent computational modeling research has demonstrated that gaze cueing is primarily driven by automatic attentional orienting mechanisms rather than controlled processing (Alister et al., 2024). If trauma and hypervigilance primarily affect controlled attention processes, they may have limited impact on the automatic mechanisms underlying basic gaze cueing.

This interpretation is consistent with research on other automatic attention processes, which have shown remarkable resilience to individual differences and clinical conditions. For example, basic orienting responses to peripheral cues remain intact in many clinical populations, even when more complex attention processes are impaired. The automatic nature of gaze following may make it less susceptible to top-down influences from trauma-related factors.

Specificity of Trauma Effects: Another possibility is that trauma-related attention alterations are specific to threatening or emotionally salient stimuli, while the neutral gaze cues used in this study may not have been sufficient to engage trauma-related attention biases. Research on attention bias in trauma populations has typically used threatening stimuli (angry faces, trauma-related words) to demonstrate effects. The neutral facial expressions and non-threatening experimental context may not have activated trauma-related attention systems.

This interpretation suggests that individual differences in trauma and hypervigilance might emerge under different experimental conditions, such as when using

emotionally expressive faces, threatening contexts, or longer exposure durations that allow for more controlled processing. Future research could test this possibility by systematically varying the emotional content and threat relevance of gaze cues.

Sample Characteristics: The null findings may also reflect characteristics of the university student sample. While participants showed meaningful variation in ACE scores and hypervigilance measures, the sample was relatively high-functioning and non-clinical. It is possible that trauma-related effects on gaze cueing only emerge in clinical populations with more severe trauma histories or current symptomatology. This interpretation is supported by research showing that trauma effects on attention are often most pronounced in individuals with clinical levels of PTSD or other trauma-related disorders. The current sample, while showing individual differences in trauma history, may not have included sufficient numbers of individuals with clinically significant trauma-related impairments to detect effects on gaze cueing.

Methodological Considerations

Several methodological factors may have contributed to the null findings. First, the gaze cueing task used relatively brief stimulus presentations and simple response requirements, which may have minimized opportunities for individual differences to emerge. Trauma-related attention effects might be more apparent in tasks requiring sustained attention, complex decision-making, or processing of ambiguous social cues.

Second, the study used a single measure of gaze cueing performance (reaction time differences), which may not capture all aspects of attention that could be influenced by trauma and hypervigilance. Eye-tracking measures, such as fixation patterns, dwell times, and saccadic responses, might reveal more subtle individual differences that are not apparent in reaction time data alone.

Third, the experimental context was highly controlled and non-threatening, which may have minimized the activation of trauma-related attention systems. Real-world social attention occurs in complex, dynamic environments where threat-related factors may play a larger role in modulating gaze following behavior.

Implications for Theory and Research

Boundaries of Trauma Effects on Social Attention

The findings contribute to understanding the boundaries of trauma's impact on social attention mechanisms. While childhood adversity clearly relates to hypervigilance and threat-related attention biases, it may not affect all aspects of social attention equally. Basic gaze cueing mechanisms appear to be relatively resilient to trauma-related individual differences, at least under the conditions tested in this study.

This pattern suggests a hierarchical model of trauma effects on attention, where automatic, evolutionarily conserved mechanisms (like gaze following) remain intact while more controlled, flexible attention processes are more susceptible to trauma-related alterations. This model has important implications for understanding both the preservation of basic social functioning and the specific domains where trauma-related impairments are most likely to emerge.

Clinical and Applied Implications

The resilience of gaze cueing mechanisms has positive implications for individuals with trauma histories. It suggests that fundamental social attention abilities remain intact, providing a foundation for social functioning and intervention efforts. This finding may be particularly relevant for trauma-focused therapies that rely on social engagement and therapeutic relationships.

However, the strong relationships between childhood adversity and hypervigilance highlight the importance of addressing trauma-related attention biases in clinical

settings. While basic gaze cueing may be preserved, the heightened vigilance and threat monitoring associated with trauma history may still interfere with social functioning in more complex or threatening contexts.

Future Research Directions

The findings suggest several important directions for future research:

Clinical Populations: Research with clinical populations, particularly individuals with PTSD or other trauma-related disorders, may reveal trauma effects on gaze cueing that were not apparent in this non-clinical sample. Clinical samples may show more pronounced trauma-related attention alterations that extend to basic social attention mechanisms.

Emotionally Salient Stimuli: Future studies should examine gaze cueing using emotionally expressive faces or threatening contexts to determine whether trauma effects emerge when stimuli are more personally relevant or threatening. The use of angry, fearful, or ambiguous facial expressions may activate trauma-related attention systems more effectively than neutral faces.

Multimodal Assessment: Incorporating eye-tracking, physiological measures, and neuroimaging techniques could provide more comprehensive assessment of attention processes and reveal subtle individual differences not captured by reaction time measures alone. These approaches might detect trauma-related alterations in attention allocation, arousal, or neural processing that are not reflected in behavioral performance.

Developmental Perspectives: Longitudinal research examining the development of gaze cueing abilities in children with trauma exposure could provide insights into how early adversity affects the emergence and maturation of social attention

mechanisms. Such research could inform early intervention efforts and identify critical periods for intervention.

Contextual Factors: Research examining gaze cueing in more naturalistic or threatening contexts may reveal individual differences that are not apparent in highly controlled laboratory settings. Virtual reality or ecological momentary assessment approaches could provide more ecologically valid assessments of social attention in real-world contexts.

Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting these findings:

Sample Characteristics

The study used a university student sample that, while showing meaningful variation in trauma history, was relatively high-functioning and non-clinical. The findings may not generalize to clinical populations or community samples with higher levels of trauma exposure or current symptomatology. Additionally, the age range was restricted to young adults, limiting generalizability across the lifespan.

Measurement Considerations

The study relied on self-report measures of childhood adversity and hypervigilance, which may be subject to recall bias, social desirability effects, or individual differences in awareness and reporting of symptoms. Objective measures of attention bias or physiological indicators of hypervigilance might provide complementary information.

The gaze cueing task used relatively simple stimuli and response requirements, which may not capture the full complexity of social attention processes that could be affected by trauma. More complex tasks involving emotional expressions, ambiguous

cues, or sustained attention might reveal individual differences not apparent in this paradigm.

Experimental Design

The experimental context was highly controlled and non-threatening, which may have minimized the activation of trauma-related attention systems. The brief stimulus presentations and simple response requirements may not have provided sufficient opportunity for individual differences to emerge.

The study used a cross-sectional design, which limits inferences about causal relationships between trauma, hypervigilance, and attention. Longitudinal research would be needed to establish temporal relationships and examine how these factors influence each other over time.

Conclusions

This study provides important insights into the relationships between childhood adversity, hypervigilance, and gaze cueing performance. The findings demonstrate that while childhood trauma is clearly associated with hypervigilance, these individual differences do not modulate basic gaze cueing mechanisms in a non-clinical sample. This pattern suggests that fundamental social attention abilities may be relatively resilient to trauma-related factors, at least under certain conditions.

The successful replication of basic gaze cueing effects and the strong relationships between trauma and hypervigilance provide confidence in the validity of the experimental procedures and measures. The absence of predicted individual difference effects, while contrary to initial hypotheses, contributes valuable information about the boundaries of trauma's impact on social attention.

The findings have important implications for both theory and practice. Theoretically, they suggest a hierarchical model of trauma effects on attention, where automatic

mechanisms remain intact while controlled processes are more susceptible to trauma-related alterations. Practically, they indicate that individuals with trauma histories retain fundamental social attention abilities, providing a foundation for social functioning and therapeutic intervention.

Future research should examine these relationships in clinical populations, with emotionally salient stimuli, and using multimodal assessment approaches to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how trauma and hypervigilance influence social attention across different contexts and populations. Such research will be crucial for developing targeted interventions and understanding the full scope of trauma's impact on social cognitive functioning.

The study contributes to a growing body of research on individual differences in social attention and highlights the complexity of relationships between early life experiences and cognitive functioning. While trauma clearly has profound effects on many aspects of psychological functioning, the current findings suggest that some fundamental social cognitive mechanisms may be more resilient than previously thought, providing hope for individuals with trauma histories and informing approaches to assessment and intervention in clinical settings.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Ethical Approval Documentation

[Ethical Approval - \(pg\) Nayanika Chatterjee - Outlook.pdf](#)

Appendix B: Participant Information Sheet and Consent Form

[Information Sheet](#)

[Debrief Form 2](#)

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Appendix C: Questionnaire Materials

ACE Questionnaire Items

[ACE-Questionnaire-for-Adults-Identified-English-rev.7.26.22.pdf](#)

Hypervigilance Questionnaire Items

[HVQ17.xlsx](#)

Appendix D: Detailed Statistical Output

[Complete Results merged.pdf](#)